

Literature Circles Learning Strategy on Students' Academic Performance in Reading Comprehension in Bayelsa State

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Abstract

The study investigated literature circles learning strategy on students' academic performance in reading comprehension in Bayelsa State. The study was guided with two objectives, two research questions and two hypotheses. The study adopted pre- test post- test quasi- experimental research design. The population for this study comprised all 9,282 senior secondary two (SS2) students in the 319 public secondary schools in Bayelsa State. Simple random sampling technique was used to select one (1) local government area for the study while disproportionate stratified random sampling technique was used in selecting one hundred (100) students for the study. Two classes were used to teach with the following methods: literature circles learning strategy and demonstration method. A pretest of Reading Comprehension Performance Test (RCPT) was given to all the students before the treatment. Thereafter, the experimental group was subjected to treatment. To establish the reliability of the instrument, Pearson Product Moment Correlation method was employed and the reliability coefficient 0.74 was obtained. Data analysis was subjected to mean scores, standard deviation and analysis of variance (ANOVA) at 0.05 alpha levels. The findings revealed that literature circles learning strategy is more effective than demonstration method. Also, the findings indicated that gender has no influence on students' performance in reading comprehension using literature circles learning strategy. Based on the findings, it was recommended among others that: The secondary school curriculum on English Language should be reviewed to include best practices in the use of literature circles learning strategy in secondary schools in Bayelsa State.

Keywords: English Language, Reading Comprehension, Learning strategy, Literature Circles and Demonstration Method

Introduction

Language is a system of arbitrary speech sounds or sequence of speech sounds which are used in interpersonal communication by an aggregation of human beings, and which rather exhaustively catalogs things, and events in the human environment. Across the globe, it has been observed that there is a huge demand for a common lingua franca so as to ensuring that the world is better united in furtherance of bringing down the wall of language hurdle that has so long prevented the world from rapidly achieving its goal of a global village, hence the need for proficiency in spoken and written English. To be properly integrated in the society, it is essential to master the *Lingua Franca* as early as possible. Ijoko et al., (2022) opined that English Language in most of the African countries is often described as a second language inasmuch as it serves to complement the mother tongue. Those who speak English as second language are often referred to as non-native speakers while those who speak English as first language are native speakers.

In the context of Nigeria educational system, the policy of the country on education places the English Language as a compulsory subject. This implies that it is mandatory for students at all levels of education, be it at the basic, senior secondary or colleges. It is a subject which candidates must pass if their overall success in the continuous assessments is to have any value. A minimum of credit pass in English Language is one of the requirements for any student seeking admission into all the tertiary institutions in Nigeria. Besides adopting English Language for effective classroom instructional performance, it is also the language of business, government and medicine (Ijoko, 2021).

However due to technological advancements, the habit of reading is being taken for granted. Students now lack the literacy skills of reading and comprehension; instead, they are fond of whirling away time on social media, engaging in unending online video streaming, online sports gambling, and so forth. This has thereby infringed negatively on their quiet time which would have been useful for reading literatures in the library or at home. Consequently, the habit of reading has turned out to become a strenuous task and a thing of the past among young ones. Even when the students read, most times, it is for remedial courses or to prepare for a very difficult examination. Students nowadays seldom read for self-development. The declining interest in reading culture among students of all ages has brought disrepute to our school system, especially at the secondary school level where innovative ideas are to be birthed through discoveries for a better tomorrow. In order to solve this unpleasant trend, it is expected that we understand the fundamentals of English Language as stated in the curriculum of secondary schools.

According to Ijoko et al., (2024), the fundamental of teaching English Language in secondary schools is to enable students develop literacy skills. Literacy skills are finessing for competence in English Language. These skills have to do with sounds of English language awareness, print awareness, and knowing the relationship between letters and sounds and how to use it better. Others include grammar and spelling, and how both function in reading and comprehension. Awareness of sounds also referred to as phonemic awareness is the ability to hear and play with the individual sounds of language so as to create new words using those sounds in different ways. Although, it is not too technical to educate students on phonemic awareness in the learning process of English Language, this usually occurs within the natural course of human development and so vital in breaking down the parts of the language for comprehension. Print awareness has to do with exposing students to various literatures involving English comprehension textbooks and short novels which go a long way to create reading culture among students thereby improving their reading ability. Knowing the relationship between letters and sounds and how to use it better stemmed from the fact that words are made up of various sounds besides just consonants and vowels.

The bottom line of literacy skills in English Language is fluency and legibility, both of which can only truly be achieved through effective reading and comprehension skills. It has also been observed from the studies carried out by Alexander (2018) that there are two crucial aspects of English Language, that is, reading and comprehension. Alexander (2018) found out in their research studies that significant relationship exists between reading and comprehension in the learning process of English Language. Reading involves a dynamic and purposeful transaction as a reader interacts with a written text (Okebukola, 2014). It therefore involves an active interaction of a reader with the text to make meaning out of it. Effective reading can be achieved when a reader reads and is able to comprehend the written text.

Comprehension has been described variously by different authorities. Collins and Cheek (2014) and Adekola (2014) described it as a process of interpreting printed symbols as meaningful units involving complex thought processes. Comprehension is a basic language skill which enables an individual to read and decode written language. Comprehension is the essence of reading and reading is key to exploration of the curriculum content of any subject.

The literacy skill of reading is one area that has not been prioritized in the post-primary school curriculum. Literacy skill is the essence of reading and without it there can be no effective learning of English Language. The poor attitude towards reading by students is a noticeable phenomenon depicting the low extent of literacy skills in secondary schools across Nigeria. The prevalent practice of the learning process in English Language class is such that students are assigned a passage to scan through and thereafter engaged in answering questions in their notes to be submitted for marking in twenty (20) minutes. In some instances, the teacher hardly creates time to correct the students or hear them out. The entire process is coded and home works are given to the students to sort themselves out in the areas they are facing difficulties in reading and comprehension.

This trend has resulted into a mono-teaching style whereby the English Language class is devoid of motivational classroom instructions which could have helped to reposition the mindsets of the students and ignite their passion for reading. Such mono-centric approach is counter-productive to the learning process of English language. This has brought to light that the classroom instructional practices in most secondary schools are unclear and lack definite direction for proper evaluation. Most English Language teachers are almost clueless to the improved theories and current concepts of teaching English as a second language Oyetunde, 2012 & Odejide, (2013).

Literature Circles (LC) have been described as small peer-led temporary discussion groups where members of diverse backgrounds meet to select, read books, make notes and contribute to an upcoming discussion meeting where every member comes up with ideas to share (Daniel, 2022). It is important to clarify that Collaboration is at the heart of literature circles practices where discussions are guided by students' responses to what they have read. Thus, literature circles empower students to freely select what they want to read based on the curriculum, form groups, read together and share what they have read with group members (Alwood, 2021).

The purpose of literature circles is to inculcate in students the skills of critical appraisal of texts, make them experience peer sharing, understanding, interpretations and comments about a text, empower them to engage in critical thinking and reflection as they read and respond to texts. Literature circles encourage creative thinking, communication, critical thinking and collaboration among learners. Thus, this strategy aims at improving the reading comprehension skills of students in order to make them more efficient readers.

Bedel (2021) looked at literature circles as teacher accompanied classroom discussion groups among English Language students or learners, who regularly get together in class to speak about and share their ideas, and comment on others' interpretations about the previously determined section of a graded reader in English, using their 'role-sheets' and student journals' in collaboration with each other. The aim is to encourage student-choice and a love of reading among young people. The idea of 'Literature Circles in English Language class defines the activity of a group of people who meet regularly to critique a specific book which they have previously read.

Accordingly, the true intent of Literature Circles is to allow students to practice and develop the skills and strategies of good readership in English as a second language. As a key element of the English Language class, Daniels (2022) explained 'Literature Circles' as a form of independent

reading, structured as collaborative small groups, and guided by reader-response principles in the light of current comprehension research. Fur (2014) stated that literature circles work like magic in that they have the power to transform English language learners from that passive, rather shy, reticent students into active students who eagerly point at their texts in order to support their arguments in the course of sharing their opinions in English. Literature circles influence reading positively among peers even as most researchers agreed that student choice is a primary factor in the selection of a text. There is also need for a teacher to be a facilitator during group discussions. Research has indicated that literature circles are used inside of the classroom within small groups that are based upon students' interest of literature. Greef (2023) addressed the issue of using literature circles side by side experiences gathered within the home by incorporating them with the strategies learned within the school setting.

Casey (2018) used the term literature circles interchangeably with that of book clubs and stated that the terms can be used to mean the same thing. She also cited research from Daniels (2022) which stated that student selection of the texts that they read is among the key principles in a given reading task. Also, Casey (2018) enforced the teacher's role as a facilitator within the book clubs by providing the students with the tools that they need for a successful group. In support of Casey's view, Daniels (2022) discussed the importance of the roles of teachers and how they are used within the literature circles. Once the students start to use the literature circles, it is important for them to use the roles that have been assigned to them by the teacher to help with the organization. After a period of acting those roles, the students will be able to interact and use the literature circles to their benefit and in such a way that they will be more independent. Daniels (2008) was able to fully explain what literature circles are and how they are used within the classroom to promote reading comprehension. Literature circles are becoming more and more present inside the classrooms as a way of instilling the strategies of guided reading so much that students can interact on their own.

On the other hand, in teaching through demonstration, students are set up to potentially conceptualise class material more effectively as shown in a study which specifically focuses on chemistry demonstrations presented by teachers (McKee et al. 2017). Demonstrations often occur when students have a hard time connecting theories to actual practice or when students are unable to understand application of theories. Teachers not only demonstrate specific learning concepts within the classroom, they can also participate in demonstration classrooms to help improve their own teaching strategies, which may or may not be demonstrative in nature. Although the literature is limited, studies showed that the effects of demonstration classroom teaching includes a change of Perspective in relating to students, more reflection in the teachers' own classroom strategies, and more personal responsibility for student learning (Bruce, 2019).

Reading with understanding is one of the most important ways through which a student can attain high academic performance in spite of the individual student's discipline. However, research has also shown that adequate attention has not been given to reading and comprehension because it has shifted from student centered to teacher centered. Adeniyi (2016) observed that reading and comprehension therefore deserves more attention than it has currently received. Student centered approaches have been advocated for the contemporary classroom and this buttresses the need to expose students to strategies that will trigger their active participation in the learning environment as prioritized in this study. Hence, it is based on the observation of students' underachievement in English Language, a phenomenon which had been largely attributed to inadequate literacy skills of reading and comprehension, that this research has taken interest in the strategy that would

enhance reading comprehension skills needed for students' optimal performance in English Language.

Statement of the Problem

Poor performance by students in English Language at the secondary school level conjoined with declining interest in reading culture has taken centre stage in the Nigerian educational system. The poor state of reading culture in Nigeria has been attributed to many factors, a few of these variables are poor quality of classroom instructional strategy, lack of teaching aid, inadequate curriculum content review, inadequate teacher training and student behaviour. This trend has remained a source of great concern to students, teachers, Non-Governmental Organisations and the government. Little wonder many scholars and researchers in Nigeria have laid claim to the fact that most English Language teachers in Nigeria are not aware of current theories, methods or principles of teaching English as a second Language.

Some scholars who have understudied this problem suggested the use of instructional strategies that are student-centered and participatory. It is against this backdrop, that this study seeks to investigate the effects of literature circles learning strategy on public secondary school students' performance in reading comprehension in Bayelsa State.

Objectives of the Study

The aim of this study is to determine the effect of literature circles learning strategy on students' performance in reading comprehension in Bayelsa State. Specifically, the study seeks to:

1. compare the difference in the mean scores of students taught reading comprehension with literature circles and those taught with demonstration method based on their pre-test and post-test scores.
2. compare the difference in the mean scores of male and female students taught reading comprehension with literature circles based on their pre-test and post-test scores.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study.

- 1) What is the difference in the mean scores of students taught reading comprehension with literature circles and those taught with demonstration method based on their pre-test and post-test scores?
- 2) What is the difference in the mean scores of male and female students taught reading comprehension with literature circles based on their pre-test and post-test scores.

Hypotheses

Two (2) null hypotheses tested at 0.05 level of significance guided this study.

1. There is no significant difference in the mean scores of students taught reading comprehension with literature circles and those taught with demonstration method based on their pre-test and post-test scores.
2. There is no significant difference in the mean scores of male and female students taught reading comprehension with literature circles based on their pre-test and post-test scores

Methodology

The study adopted the pre-test post-test quasi- experimental research design. The population of the study comprised all the 19, 282 senior secondary SS 2 students in the 319 public secondary schools in Bayelsa State. (Source: Bayelsa State Post Primary Schools Board, office of the Directorate of Inspection and Statistics, 2024). Sample sizes of one hundred (100) senior secondary SS 2 students were used for this study. A simple random sampling and stratified random sampling techniques were used to compose the sample. Simple random sampling was used to draw one (1) local government area from the eight (8) of them in the state. It was done by writing out the names of the eight (8) local government areas on a piece of paper. The eight (8) pieces of paper bearing the respective names of the local government areas were thoroughly shuffled in a container and one (1) of it was randomly drawn without replacement.

After drawing the one (1) local government area by simple random sampling, a disproportionate stratified random sampling was used to draw two schools from the educational zones in the local government area for the study. Twenty (20) items multiple choice test entitled “Reading Comprehension Performance Test” (RCPT) was used in this research to determine students’ academic performance. The face and content validity of the instrument was validated by the researcher’s supervisor and two experts in the Department of Foundations, Arts and Social Science Education, Federal University Otuoke. The instrument was modified based on the suggestions of these experts before administration.

To establish the reliability of the instrument, Pearson Product Moment Correlation method was adopted. This is used in order to determine the internal consistency of the test items. Therefore, twenty (20) students who were not part of the sample size were selected using simple random sampling technique from a neighboring school within the selected local government. Twenty (20) copies of the Reading Comprehension Performance Test (RCPT) were administered to them. The RCPT was administered to this group of students and the reliability coefficient of 0.74 was obtained. However, the test was given to the two groups as pre-test. Therefore, the experimental group was treated. The students in the experimental group were exposed to lessons developed using literature circles learning strategy. Then, the same test items were reshuffled and administered as post-test in order to find out the academic performance of the students. The mean and standard deviation was used to answer the research questions while Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 alpha levels.

Result

Table 4.1: Mean, Standard Deviation of Students Taught Reading Comprehension Using Literature Circles and those Taught with Demonstration Method.

Method	Pre- test			Post – test		Actual Score
	N	\bar{x}	SD	\bar{x}	SD	
Literature Circle Strategy	54	38.70	7.28	69.30	10.50	30.60
Demonstration Method	46	16.70	4.91	33.20	6.71	16.50

Table 1 showed that students taught reading comprehension with literature circles learning strategy had a mean score and a standard deviation of 38.70 and 7.28 during the pre-test while students that were taught reading comprehension using demonstration method had a mean and standard

deviation of 16.70 and 4.91. After post-test, students taught with literature circles learning strategy had a mean score of 69.30 and standard deviation of 10.50 while those taught using demonstration method had a mean score of 33.20 and standard deviation of 6.71. The mean difference for students taught with literature circles learning strategy was 30.60 while students taught using discussion method was 16.50. This indicated that students taught with literature circles learning strategy performed better than the students taught with demonstration method.

Table 2: Mean, Standard Deviation, and Actual Score of Male and Female Students' Performance in Reading Comprehension Using Literature Circles Learning Strategy.

Gender	Pre- test			Post – test		Actual Score
	N	\bar{x}	SD	\bar{x}	SD	
Male	26	34.42	7.53	75.96	7.35	41.54
Female	24	35.00	8.60	74.38	6.96	39.38

Table 2 showed the analysis of the performance of male and female students taught reading comprehension using literature circles learning strategy. Male students taught with literature circles learning strategy at the pre-test had the mean score of 34.42 and standard deviation of 7.53 while female students exposed to literature circles learning strategy had the mean score of 35.00 and standard deviation of 8.60. Male students taught with literature circles learning strategy at post-test had the mean score of 75.96 and standard deviation of 7.35 with mean gain of 41.54, while female students exposed to literature circles learning strategy had the mean score of 74.38 and standard deviation of 6.96 with mean gain of 39.38. This indicated that the difference was in favour of male students.

Hypothesis Table 3: Summary of ANCOVA of Students Taught Reading Comprehension Using Literature Circles and those Taught with Demonstration Method.

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	12244.511 ^a	2	6122.255	126.582	.000	.723
Intercept	21136.922	1	21136.922	437.021	.000	.818
Pretest	144.511	1	144.511	2.988	.087	.030
Methods	11931.542	1	11931.542	246.693	.000	.718
Error	4691.489	97	48.366			
Total	567500.000	100				
Corrected Total	16936.000	99				

Table 3 showed that the analysis of variance in the performance mean scores of students taught reading comprehension using literature circles learning strategy and those taught using the demonstration method yielded an F 1,97 of 246.693 with associated exact probability value of 0.001. Since the associated probability (0.001) was less than 0.05, the null hypothesis was rejected. Thus, there was a significant difference between the mean scores of students taught reading

comprehension with literature circles learning strategy and those taught with demonstration Method.

Table 4: Summary of ANOVA of Male and Female students Taught Reading Comprehension Using Literature Circles Learning Strategy

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	32.591 ^a	2	16.295	.311	.734	.013
Intercept	11189.911	1	11189.911	213.322	.000	.819
Pretest	1.178	1	1.178	.022	.882	.000
Gender	30.930	1	30.930	.590	.446	.012
Error	2465.409	47	52.456			
Total	365450.000	50				
Corrected Total	2498.000	49				

Table 4 showed that the analysis of variance in the performance mean scores of male and female students taught reading comprehension with literature circles learning strategy yielded an F 1,47 of 0.590 with associated exact probability value of 0.446. Since the associated probability (0.446) was greater than 0.05, the null hypothesis was accepted. Thus, there was no significant difference between the mean performance scores of male and female students taught reading comprehension with literature circles learning strategy.

Summary of findings

The results obtained after data analysis are summarised as follows:

1. Literature circle learning strategy had a significant effect on the performance of students in reading comprehension as compared to demonstration methods.
2. Male students taught reading comprehension using literature circles learning strategy performed better than the female students.
2. There was a significant difference between the mean performance score of students taught reading comprehension with literature circles learning strategy and those taught with demonstration method.
3. There was no significant difference between the mean scores of students taught reading comprehension with literature circles learning strategy and those taught with demonstration method.

Discussion of the Findings

Literature Circles Learning Strategy and Students' performance.

The result shown in table 4.1 revealed that the mean difference of students exposed to literature circles strategy greatly influenced the performance of students in reading comprehension. This finding agreed with the findings by Thomas (2013) and Ijoko (2024). These studies reported a positive effect on students' comprehension ability when teachers adopted a small group based programme in teaching reading comprehension. Thomas (2013) as cited in Marilyn et al, (2021) reported that students who engaged in literature circles made more gain in reading comprehension

than their counterparts who were not so engaged. This is because literature circles provide students the opportunity to engage in interactive book talks in a very natural way. Thus, students are able to secure a connection between the stories they read and their life experiences leading to a better understanding of what is read. This study is at variance with the study of Shannon (2019) who reported no significant difference between students exposed to the use of literature circles in the classroom and those who did not engage in this form of instruction.

Influence Gender on Students' Performance in Reading comprehension Using Literature Circles.

Table 2 showed that male students performed better than their female counterparts when exposed to literature circles. This implies that both male and female students benefited from the treatment but the males outperformed their female counterparts. The result is in disagreement with the findings of Cherland (2019) which reported that in every mixed-gender group, the boys spoke for longer turns, engaged in more teasing of the girls, and displayed more contradictions. However, the findings agreed with Ijoko (2021) and Ugboja and Ijoko (2023) who indicated that when both the males and the females were exposed to this treatment, they performed in related level with a slide difference in favour of the males as a result of chance. This again, implies that the interaction in gender is not a strong determinant to students' performance in reading comprehension as advocated in an earlier research work by Guiller and Dumdell (2017) who in their findings asserted that males and females were similar regarding the use of linguistic variables.

Recommendations

Based on the analysis and findings of this study, the following were recommended:

1. The secondary school curriculum on English Language should be reviewed to include best practices in the use of literature circles learning strategy in secondary schools in Bayelsa State and across the whole federation.
2. The English teachers in secondary schools in Bayelsa State should be provided mandatory professional development programme so as to increase their capacity to implement the reviewed curriculum.
3. The government should endeavour to provide the English teachers with the necessary infrastructure from time to time that will be sufficient enough to implement the use of literature circles learning strategy in secondary schools in Bayelsa State.
4. The male students should as well be given more attention in the development of their reading comprehension skills by encouraging them to take more roles in the activities of literature circles in reading comprehension while the female students should be encouraged with incentives for best performance so as to balance the performance level in the class.

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